

Solar-based energy resilience in future cities – a preliminary study in the Sub-Sunbelt region

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Abstract- The metrics of future Smart cities are complex and ask for interdisciplinary approach. Energy portfolio and the ratio of self-consumption / sufficiency are key performance indexes for providing city long-term sustainability. Targeting 100% renewables production for mitigating climate change threats ask also for challenging solutions. As Europe is not enjoying the Sunbelt climate but still showed clear commitment towards high renewables penetration, the paper addresses the feasibility of a scenario targeting electrical energy production with 100% renewables and complete self-sufficiency in the so-called Sub-Sunbelt region. A preliminary study is analyzing in terms of key performance indexes related to renewables production and self-sufficiency specific cities in a lower half of Europe, coined as being a Sub-Sunbelt region. For this, selected cities from the Sub-Sunbelt region (from 35° to 50° latitude north) in Greece, Italy, Spain, Portugal, Romania, Austria, Germany and France have been chosen, by also making a comparison with sunny Sunbelt based cities Rabat, Dubai and Cairo. The study suggests that self-sufficiency and resilience with solar based renewables is reachable in Sub-Sunbelt regions, and that important renewables-based H₂/CH₄ long-term storage and consumption resources are also needed to cope with the cold seasons, while the Sunbelt regions can become exporters of renewables-based H₂/CH₄ by using their surplus energy during the summer time.

Keywords: Smart City, self-sufficiency, Sunbelt, Sub-Sunbelt, renewable energy sources, PV, power to gas, Summer/Winter.

I. SUNBELT AND SUB-SUNBELT REGIONS

The metrics of Smart cities are complex and ask for interdisciplinary approach. Energy portfolio and the ratio of self-consumption are key performance indexes (KPIs) for city sustainability. Targeting 100% renewable energy sources (RES) ask also for challenging solutions, but this target is also part of the request to be resilient, as for instance photovoltaics (PV) production is available everywhere where there is acceptable solar radiation, so it can be produced inside the city or in nearby regions. Increased local production avoids high dependency on remote areas with bulk energy production and on high voltage network of the

national or regional (e.g. European) network, which should eventually cover only 5 to 20% levels of energy exchange.

It is already known the so called “Sunbelt” region, which is characterized by sunny weather with high solarization all over the year. In geographical terms, it means either a certain number of countries [1] or more simplified a certain latitude band, between 15 and 35 degrees, having the tropics as approximate middle of the North and South Sunbelt regions. Figure 1 presents a Sunbelt region based on simplified geographical bands described by latitudes. It can be observed that the Sunbelt regions overlap with a part of the tropical region. The reason why only a part of the entire tropical region in the Sunbelt area is due to the fact that near equator it is a special climate which can be hot but also can have frequent rains which make the region to have less sunny periods during the day time than in the Sunbelt region.

Fig. 1 Sunbelt regions – a simplified latitude-based definition

The Sunbelt regions treated also at country-level are the so-called tropical climates countries, according to Köppen climate classification and are presented in figure 2.

Fig. 2 Areas of the world with subtropical climates according to Köppen climate classification

The figure shows relatively similar “sunbelt” regions comparing with the previous latitude-based definition.

By concentrating more on European, North African and Middle East region we can define as well a certain latitude-based region which is positioned in the North of the Sunbelt region and has also acceptable solarization, being suitable as well for large deployments of PV plants.

In figure 3 is proposed such latitude-based area which can be named Sub-Sunbelt (SSB) region, lying between 35- and 50-degrees latitude, thus being limited in the North to the middle of the moderate climate region.

Figure 3 – Sub-Sunbelt (SSB) region

By analysing different data from [2], it can be concluded that the Sunbelt area is characterized by more than 1500 kWh/year production for each kW of traditional installed PV (e.g. with around 15% conversion efficiency, as a conservative technology approach) and that the Sub-Sunbelt area can provide, based on the specific locality, between 1000 and 1600 kWh/year for the same kWp of installed PV.

The remaining moderate climate region, in the northern part of Europe – beyond the Sub-Sunbelt region, respectively between 50° and 66° (up to Arctic circle) has usually less than 1000 kWh/year for a PV installation of 1 kWp .

In the Sunbelt region there is plenty of direct energy from sun, which make possible scenarios with up to 100% renewables by using only PV production; this solar irradiation abundancy made possible record low energy production costs in recent auctions, down to 1.77 c/kWh in PPA contracts [3]. It gives also good grounds to show high self-sufficiency for future smart cities, in order to increase their immunity, self-sufficiency and resilience.

The paper is assessing if the sub-sunbelt region is also proper for producing entire or a big share of energy with PV technologies in cities, helped also by their nearby metropolitan areas. PV is essential for such self-sufficiency analysis in cities, because we cannot rely usually on wind based production in cities, as the wind is usually not enough blowing in such urban entities, or if it has a certain potential it brings more lack of comfort in cities than in country regions.

Recent analysis [4] showed that even cities such as Utrecht from Holland, in specific districts such as Lombok, if are used all available roofs, it can reached 60% of energy self-

sufficiency in the city district. In this city only 5% of roof spaces are populated with PV panels, which represent 17 MW, but if using the entire available surface, the production of 340 MWp may cover only 6.8% of the municipal area, for a conservative specific area of 20 m² per kWp installed. It can be inferred that 6.8% of municipal area is sufficient to get 60% of energy production of a city in the Utrecht region, having a latitude which is already nearby the upper limit of Sub-Sunbelt region.

This deduction gives good inputs for considering that in the Sub-Sunbelt region, e.g. when getting around 1200 kWh/year/kWp, one can reach near full self-sufficiency in smart cities helped by their surroundings.

In order to assess the self-sufficiency of Sub-Sunbelt cities, an important factor is the rate of city and surroundings area which can be used to mount PV panels. Such studies have been already performed in some regions of the world. For instance, California has been shown to have great potential to offset electricity use — as its rooftop PV could generate 74% of the electricity sold by its utilities in 2013 [5]. The same study shows that the total national technical potential of rooftop PV is 1,118 gigawatts (GW) of installed capacity and 1,432 terawatt-hours (TWh) of annual energy generation. This equates to 39% of total national electric-sector sales. Moreover, Small building rooftops could accommodate 731 GW of PV capacity and generate 926 TWh/year of PV energy, which represents approximately 65% of rooftop PV’s total technical potential. These results are sensitive to assumptions about module performance, which is expected to continue improving over time. For example, this analysis assumed a module efficiency of 16% to represent a mixture of various technology types. For the analysis it has been assumed a module power density of 160 W/m², corresponding to a module efficiency of approximately 16%.

II. ASSESSMENT APPROACH

The following sections will apply a common assessment procedure, in order to give key performance indexes (KPIs) related to energy self-sufficiency in the cities of the future.

The following formulas have been used:

a) E_{AVRG} , as average PV energy production per year, for a PV panel of 1 kWp

$$E_{AVRG} = \sum E_{MO}(i) / 12 \quad (1)$$

where $E_{MO}(i)$ is PV energy production potential in month i , where $i=1..12$, values which have been obtained in this study from [2]. E_{AVRG} is measured in kWh/month, noted kWh/m. $K_{S/W}$ as Summer / winter energy production ratio:

$$K_{S/W} = E_{MAX_mo} / E_{MIN_mo} \quad (2)$$

where E_{MAX_mo} and E_{MIN_mo} are monthly maximum and minimum values of PV energy production potential in the studied city.

b) Yearlong monthly energy production deviation

$$E_{OVER} = \max((E_{MONTH}(i) - E_{AVRG}) \quad (3)$$

$$E_{UNDER} = \min((E_{MONTH}(i) - E_{AVRG}) \quad (4)$$

As can be expected, $E_{OVER(i)}$ is always positive and the month is in summer period, while $E_{UNDER(i)}$ is always negative and the month belongs to winter season.

c) *Self-sufficiency factor*

$$K_{SELF-CONS} = S_{CITY} * K_{USE} * E_{YEAR_PV} / S_{1kW} / E_{Y_CITY} \quad (5)$$

$$E_{Y_CITY} = E_{AVRG_PER_CAPITA} * P_{CITY} \quad (6)$$

where S_{CITY} is the surface of the city, K_{USE} is the percentage of city surface which can be used for PV installations, E_{YEAR} is the yearly production for a PV installation of 1 kWp, S_{1kW} is the surface needed to install 1 kWp of PV panels and E_{Y_CITY} is the average yearly consumption of the city. As more clear data is not usually easy to be obtained, E_{Y_CITY} is calculated in a simplified manner by using the average consumption of the country multiplied by the city population P_{CITY} . $E_{AVRG_PER_CAPITA}$ is taken for convenience from public statistics, specifically in this paper being chosen [6].

d) *Extended metropolitan surface needed (S_{NEC}) for 100% self-consumption*

$$S_{NEC} [\%] = 1 / K_{SELF-CONS} * K_{USE} / K_{USE_EXT} \quad (7)$$

where K_{USE_EXT} is the usage factor for PV installations which is acceptable for extended metropolitan area; usually, K_{EXT} can be higher than in the city, as it is more space which can be used by co-sharing agricultural areas. The S_{NEC} factor shows how much is needed to be extended the PV production in nearby metropolitan area in order to complete the energy need for a total regional self-sufficiency.

Based on the Utrecht situation, we chose $K_{USE} = 6\%$ and $K_{USE_EXT} = 10\%$, as a practical value which can be implemented in each city. In the situations that the self-sufficiency exceeds factor 1, a reduced K_{USE} has been chosen for getting 100% self-sufficiency. This situation may occur in cities with low density of population, allowing a higher PV penetration in the municipal area.

Several cities in the sub-Sunbelt region will be assessed. As even the sub-sunbelt region is relatively large, we analyze separately the south half of the sub-sunbelt, to be named “*lower sub-sunbelt*” (L-SSB) and the north half of the sub-sunbelt, to be named “*upper sub-sunbelt*” (U-SSB), also shown in Figure 3. Three additional cities placed in the sunbelt region are also analyzed, to have a comparison with the sub-sunbelt region.

III. LOWER SUB-SUNBELT CITY CASES – ATHENS, MADRID, ROME AND LISBON

To assess the sustainability of lower sub-sunbelt (L-SBB) cities it has been chosen Athens, the capital of Greece, as well as the Spanish, Italian and Portuguese capitals Madrid, Rome and Lisbon, with specific PV production capability and with latitude information shown in the Figure 4.

They are European cities placed in the “lower sub-sunbelt” region, according to the previous section proposed classification. Madrid has a municipal area of 604 km² [7] while Athens has 412 km² of municipal area [8].

Figure 4 – Athens / Greece, Madrid / Spain, Rome / Italy, Lisbon / Portugal and their yearly energy production

Metropolitan area and their corresponding populations have been considered for the assessment. The city consumption has been based on average country consumption for a citizen and a factor of multiplicity has been also taken into consideration in order to represent the additional industry-related consumption which is specific for most of the cities.

The monthly energy production with 1 kWp of PV panels is presented in table 1 for Athens, Madrid and Rome. Information is provided from the interactive portal [2].

Table 1 – Monthly PV energy production in Athens, Madrid and Rome

Month	Athens		Madrid		Rome	
	E_m	H_m	E_m	H_m	E_m	H_m
Jan	92.2	116	89.2	110	76.2	95.5
Feb	99.3	126	106	133	95.1	121
Mar	147	189	141	184	125	163
Apr	151	198	136	181	132	175
May	161	215	145	198	147	199
Jun	164	223	150	208	151	209
Jul	164	227	163	231	164	229
Aug	161	223	159	225	159	221
Sep	149	204	141	194	132	180
Oct	131	174	125	164	112	148
Nov	100	129	94.6	120	81.1	104
Dec	82.2	103	87.8	109	73.9	93.2
Year avrg.	133	177	128	171	121	161
Total/year	1600	2130	1540	2060	1450	1940

where E_m is the average monthly electricity production from the given system (kWh) and H_m is the average sum of global irradiation per square meter received by the modules of the given system (kWh/m²). The H_m values shows maximal energy which can be obtained from sun, if entire areas are used and the conversion efficiency would be 100%.

Figure 5 shows the monthly energy production ($E_{MO(i)}$ from relation (1)) evolution in all selected locations, over the whole year. The sum of the monthly energies give the yearly production (Total/year) shown also in Figures 4 and 5. Figure 6 suggests that there is a similarity between the energy production pattern in the two cities, as a characteristic specific for lower sub-sunbelt cities (placed between 35° and 42.5° North latitude), which are placed at the latitude of the European Mediterranean area.

Figure 5 – Graph with monthly energy production in lower sub-Sunbelt cities Athens, Madrid, Rome and Lisbon

By applying the formulas of the previous chapter, as an example, we obtain e.g. for Madrid:

$$\begin{aligned} E_{AVRG_MADRID} &= 128.3 \text{ kWh/m;} \\ K_{S/W_SPAIN} &= 1.86; \\ E_{OVER_MADRID} &= 35 \text{ kWh;} \\ E_{UNDER_MADRID} &= -40.2 \text{ kWh;} \end{aligned}$$

The self-consumption factor $K_{SELF-CONS}$ and the necessary area to cover entire city consumption (represented through the factor S_{NEC}) are presented in the synthesis chapter.

The summer to winter factor is nearly 2 (respectively 1.98 and 1.86), meaning that there is a need to store on long term energy in the summer (e.g. as hydrogen – H_2 or CH_4 from renewable electricity) and to use it in the winter time. E_{OVER} are always lower than E_{UNDER} factors, showing that a longer period in the warmer period is needed for storing at lower power and a shorter period in cold times is necessary to be covered.

IV. UPPER SUB-SUNBELT CITIES: BUCHAREST, VIENNA, MUNICH AND PARIS

Bucharest (Romania), Vienna (Austria), Munich (Germany) and Paris (France) are all in the Upper Sub-sunbelt (U-SSB) region, meaning between 42.5° and 50° North latitude, as they can be seen in Figure 6.

Figure 6 – Bucharest / Romania, Vienna / Austria, Munich / Germany, Paris / France and its yearly energy production

Figure 8 shows the energy production evolution in both locations over the entire year.

Figure 7 – Graph with monthly energy production in upper sub-Sunbelt cities Bucharest, Vienna, Paris and Munich

By applying the formulas of the previous chapter, we obtain e.g. for Bucharest and Vienna:

$$\begin{aligned} E_{AVRG_BUCHAREST} &= 102 \text{ kWh/m;} & E_{AVRG_VIENNA} &= 88.2 \text{ kWh/m;} \\ K_{S/W_BUCHAREST} &= 3.49; & K_{S/W_VIENNA} &= 4.23; \\ E_{OVER_BUCHAREST} &= 43 \text{ kWh;} & E_{UNDER_BUCHAREST} &= -60 \text{ kWh;} \\ E_{OVER_VIENNA} &= 40.8 \text{ kWh;} & E_{UNDER_VIENNA} &= -57.7 \text{ kWh;} \end{aligned}$$

The self-consumption factor $K_{SELF-CONS}$ and the metropolitan area factor S_{NEC} are presented in the synthesis chapter.

The summer to winter $K_{S/W}$ factor is 3.5 to 4.2, meaning that there is a high need to store on long term energy in the summer (H_2 or CH_4 from renewable electricity) and to use it in the winter time. E_{OVER} are also for these cities lower than E_{UNDER} factors. The high values of $K_{S/W}$ suggest that the alternative renewables-based (RES) energy streams based on H_2 or CH_4 are a must for these regions, if only PV production is foreseen as source of energy for high level of local self-sufficiency.

The reconversion of H_2/CH_4 in electrical energy during the winter period, to be achieved with CHP solutions, is benefic for the cities end-users, as the heat associated with the energy production is also necessary during cold periods. The lower sub-sunbelt situation suggests also that the use of remote bulk production based on wind can reduce the amount of H_2 or CH_4 facilities in these regions.

V. SUNBELT CITY CASES – RABAT, CAIRO AND DUBAI

Rabat (Maroc), Cairo (Egypt) and Dubai (UAE) are cities placed in the sunbelt area, meaning a latitude in the 15 to 35° range. Figure 8 presents the energy production evolution in these locations over the entire year, showing similarity of energy production inside the sunbelt area.

Figure 8 – Graph with monthly energy production in Sunbelt cities Rabat, Dubai and Cairo

By applying the formulas of the previous chapter, we obtain as an example for Rabat and Dubai cities:

$$\begin{aligned} E_{AVRG_RABAT} &= 139 \text{ kWh/m;} & E_{AVRG_DUBAI} &= 148 \text{ kWh/m;} \\ K_{S/W_RABAT} &= 1.50; & K_{S/W_DUBAI} &= 1.24; \\ E_{OVER_RABAT} &= 23 \text{ kWh;} & E_{UNDER_RABAT} &= -31 \text{ kWh;} \\ E_{OVER_DUBAI} &= 15 \text{ kWh;} & E_{UNDER_DUBAI} &= -17 \text{ kWh;} \end{aligned}$$

$K_{SELF-CONS}$ and S_{NEC} are presented in the next synthesis chapter. A special situation occurs in Dubai city, where the high density of population asks for a large extended region to cover all energy consumption, while Rabat is capable to be self-sustained by its current municipal area.

The summer to winter factor is very low in the sunbelt region (closer to the ideal case of having constant PV production over the entire year), from 1.24 to 1.5, meaning that there is a moderate-low need to store on long term energy in the summer (H_2 or CH_4 from renewable electricity) and to use it in the winter time.

The low values of $K_{S/W}$ suggest that the alternative energy streams based on H_2 or CH_4 are not crucial for these regions, if only PV production is foreseen as source of energy. The production of H_2/CH_4 in electrical energy during the summer period can be a way for sunbelt regions to become energy exporters of RES-based H_2 or CH_4 .

The feasibility of high self-production in the sunbelt area is confirmed by the Chinese city of Hangzhou, which intends that 60% of its energy consumption to come from renewable sources by the end of 2020. Within this goal, PV will play a huge part in reaching that target as it is already installed a capacity of 1 GW, to be followed by another 700 MW till the end of 2020 [13].

VI. SYNTHESIS

Figure 9 gives a comparison of the PV production over an entire year for each of the selected cities. It can be observed how monthly energy production is decreasing for sub-sunbelt cities (for both U-SSB and L-SSB) compared with sunbelt-positioned cities (SB).

Figure 9 – Comparison of energy production over a year

The graph shows that there is more continuity in PV production over the year in the sunbelt region and that this is degrading in the sub-sunbelt region, with higher degradation in the upper sub-sunbelt area.

For underlining the difference, Figure 10 shows the summer / winter production ratio $K_{S/W}$ in selected cities, which is small in sunbelt region but becomes very high in the upper sub-sunbelt area.

Fig. 10 – Summer/winter energy production $K_{S/W}$ ratio in selected cities

This situation suggests that in order to fulfill 100% RES production it is needed to store energy in summer and consume it in winter, by using long-term storage such as RES-based produced hydrogen and/or CH_4 (green hydrogen and CH_4). The capacity of such stored energy during summer and of producing back electrical energy and heat during winter is depicted in Figure 11. The more we advance towards north of sub-sunbelt region the more it is needed higher capacity for long-term storage.

The Figure suggests that for lower sub-sunbelt region it is needed around two times more long-storage resources than in the sunbelt region, while in the upper sub-sunbelt region are needed three to four times more long-storage resources. This aspects shows that in the sunbelt region the difference between summer and winter is not a big concern even if PV production is considered as sole source of energy in a year, and that the winter energy coverage may be solved by higher PV capacity, while in the summer the extra energy can be converted in H_2 or CH_4 and exported, as a changing energy export paradigm comparing with today export of oil.

Figure 11 – Min and Max deviation from average energy production

In the meantime, the sub-sunbelt regions ask for finding solutions for long-term storage, which may ask also for a different strategy of covering winter energy needs. Such solution can rely on bulk production at high distance (traditional today solution), thus overpassing the danger of having no RES production during dark and calm days, the so called “*Dunkelflaute*” (calm and dark period) period [14], or on a combination with CH_4 and/or H_2 storage, obtained from the summer time and from remote locations, including from sunbelt regions.

Table 2 gives a synthetic view of $K_{\text{SELF-CONS}}$ (presented as the column “Self”, from formula (5)).

Table 2 – Synthetic self-consumption KPIs in European cities

	City	Area	k_use	m2	E/kWp	E_PV/y	P_PV	Self
	popul	km2		/kWp	/year	MWh		
Rome	2.87	1285	4.0%	12	1450	6,211	4,283	29.9%
Madrid	3.223	604	4.0%	12	1540	3,101	2,013	10.2%
Athens	3.09	412	4.0%	12	1600	2,197	1,373	9.0%
Bucharest	1.883	228	4.0%	12	1220	927	760	13.2%
Lisbon	0.505	100	4.0%	12	1620	540	333	15.6%
Viena	1.889	414	4.0%	12	1060	1,463	1,380	6.2%
Paris	12.4	14500	4.0%	12	1040	50,267	48,333	40.4%
Munchen	1.46	310	4.0%	12	1040	1,075	1,033	7.6%

The cities KPIs show that several levels of self-sufficiency can be obtained, from 6.2% up to 40%, which can be also used for providing resilience against power supply from outside. Consumption is based on official figures from [8] and on scaling factors which consider higher consumption with industry considered to have activity in the city area. To be noted that the self-sufficiency is highly dependent on the area considered for the city, thus the results can be changed if higher or lower area around the city are taken into consideration for the PV deployments.

The table presents figures in a scenario which considers current PV technology (conservative). However, emerging new PV technologies (bi-facial, quantum dots, perovskite, graphene, PV incorporated in the building’s windows, PV incorporated in the walls – with low efficiency but high area potential etc.) may request reduced areas for the same energy production, thus being able to increase the Self KPI with 50% or even more on longer term.

VII. CONCLUSIONS

The paper gives some synthetic KPIs for assessing self-sufficient solar-based energy in future cities, to be used also for resilience against outside energy supply shortages. The cities have been chosen in two geographical regions, the sunbelt (SB) and the sub-sunbelt (SSB) region, while the latest is also divided in lower and upper part (L-SSB and U-SSB). The analysis is focused on European cities placed in the sub-sunbelt region and makes a comparison with sunbelt located cities which are not far from Europe.

The study uses specific KPIs for assessing each of the three latitude-based geographical bands and shows that high penetration of PVs for obtaining solar-based energy is possible in all the regions, with significant self-sufficiency and with good prospects for improving resilience. The KPI have good potential to be improved if higher surrounding areas are considered to serve the cities PV deployment and they will be positively influenced by emerging technologies in PV panels. However, due to higher difference between winter and summer PV energy production ($K_{S/W}$ range is from 1.9 to 4.2), additional long-term storage is needed in sub-sunbelt regions to flatten the yearly production pattern.

The study suggests that the $K_{S/W}$ ratio can indicate that sub-sunbelt cities can extensively develop RES-based H_2 and CH_4 installations for both production and consumption, while sunbelt cities might invest in PV installations and H_2/CH_4 installations for power-to-gas (P2G) production (green gas), aiming export of energy for the winter needs in SSB countries, as a shift from the today paradigm based mainly on fossil fuel.

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